

THE EFFECTS OF TIDAL ELEVATION AND WIND/WAVE EXPOSURE ON OYSTER
RECRUITMENT IN SAN DIEGO BAY, CALIFORNIA

by

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1. Abstract

Human introduced habitats such as seawalls and pier piles in California coastal areas have led to increased erosion and shoreline loss. Oyster restoration may reduce shoreline loss by reintroducing complex structure that slows wave action. The Port of San Diego installed spherical concrete Living Shoreline structures (“reef balls”) on the mudflats of the Chula Vista Wildlife Reserve in San Diego Bay to protect shorelines while also increasing native oyster (*Ostrea lurida*) populations and discouraging recruitment by non-native Pacific oysters (*Magallana gigas*). We surveyed the reef balls to determine the abundance and relative cover of native and non-native oysters to understand the distribution of both species relative to wind exposure and tidal elevation. We found that native oysters occupy more space on reef balls than non-native oysters, but only on the outside of reef balls at lower elevations. Tidal elevation also had a significant effect on both species in which native oyster densities increased and non-native oyster densities decreased with lower elevations. However, there was no significant wind/wave action effect on oyster recruitment. These findings will contribute to efforts by the Port of San Diego to further adapt the building and construction of Living Shorelines to restore the population of native oysters and reduce erosion in San Diego Bay.

2. Introduction

2.1 Climate Change

Climate change has severely impacted a myriad of ecosystems globally. The increasing temperatures caused by an accumulation greenhouse gasses in the atmosphere has melted glaciers and increased evaporation, in turn causing a rise in sea level (Hartig, 2002). As the sea

rises, the coasts have been enduring intensified hydrologic cycles with violent storms and increased wave height causing inundation, or flooding, of estuaries. A study by Hartig et al. looked further into the effects of the rising sea level on wetland loss in the Jamaica Bay, New York. They found that over time, the percentage of marsh loss in the Jamaica Bay has been increasing over the decades since 1959 (Hartig, 2002). This shoreline erosion has therefore impacted the ecosystems of organisms who reside along those shorelines. To combat eroding shorelines, restoration efforts have focused on measures that can reduce erosion and increase total sedimentation to preserve or increase shoreline elevation (Parker, 2019).

2.2 Armoring Shorelines

Due to the severe effects of climate change on the shorelines of the west coast of the United States, efforts to armor the shorelines from further erosion are in place. Examples of methods to protect the shorelines include placing bulky substrate such as riprap, bulkheads, seawalls, or pier piles (Griggs, 2009) along the shoreline. In this study, a method of armoring shorelines is utilized with living shorelines made up of reef balls. (Perog et al., 2023; Griggs, 2009) Reef balls, referred to as a “living shoreline,” are a “green-gray” solution to eroding shorelines and declining native oyster populations (Latta and Boyer, 2015). They are a “green-gray” model because they incorporate artificial and natural materials to reduce the carbon footprint and encourage native oyster recruitment. Reef balls were also specifically designed to reduce the impact of wave action on the shoreline they protect (Buccino et al., 2014).

2.3 Ostrea Lurida

The Olympia oyster, *Ostrea lurida*, is the only native oyster species along the west coast of the

United States. Their habitat range is from Baja California, Mexico to British Columbia, Canada (Tronske et al., 2018). They are primarily found in estuaries, which are inland bays of mixing freshwater and saltwater (Dyer, 1973). This is due to their sensitivity to high levels of salinity in marine environments (Bagget et al., 2014). Within the shore, Olympia oysters are found at specific tidal elevations due to their ability to survive periods of desiccation, which may be between hours to days at a time (Trimble et al., 2009). *O. lurida* reaches its maximum density at or below +0.2 m MLLW (Tronske et al., 2018). Oysters in general are essential to the health of shoreline ecosystems as they are a foundation species that provides structurally complex reef habitats for other organisms with their robust and durable calcium carbonate shells (Perog et al., 2023). They allow many other marine organisms, such as tunicates, arthropods, and mollusks a surface to settle and thrive on. Although oysters may survive long periods out of water, they rely on their gills for respiration and must filter water between their two valves to survive. But since these shellfish must filter water for gas exchange, they also filter out waste, thus improving the health of surrounding ecosystem. However, oysters are also capitalized on as a food source, and have been experiencing over-harvesting as a result. Additionally, they are suffering from various human interventions such as pollution, construction, and destruction of wetlands (Zu Ermgassen, 2012; Alan, 2009). With copious negative impacts on Olympia oysters, the population has been drastically depleting. Native oysters are now one of the least known shellfish because the population has declined down to 90% (Beck et al., 2011). There are restoration efforts underway by the Port of San Diego to construct solutions to favor the recruitment of native oysters along the west coast (Perog et al., 2023).

2.4 *Magallana gigas*

The Pacific oyster, *Magallana gigas* (previously *Crassostrea gigas*), is an oyster native to Japan that was imported to the United States in the 1900s (Dias, 2022). *M. gigas* is known to be a non-indigenous species, or NIS, that has had an invasive effect on native species (Dias, 2022). They are considered to be invasive due to the competition for food and space of habitat (Schaefer, 1937). *M. gigas* achieve their highest densities and recruit at higher tidal elevations than *O. lurida* (+0.4 m MLLW) (Tronske et al., 2018, Perog et al. 2023), however their elevational range still overlaps with native oysters. Due to this overlap, *M. gigas* may compete and negatively impact the native *O. lurida*.

2.5 Factors That Influence Oyster Recruitment

The Port of San Diego engineered and placed 360 reef balls into the San Diego Bay at the Chula Vista Wildlife Reserve (CVWR) site in efforts to restore the native oyster population. The reef balls were specifically designed for encouraging maximum *O. lurida* recruitment by modifying the composition and rugosity of the concrete. Previous studies have identified recruitment patterns of oysters on horizontal and vertical substrates. Oysters prefer to recruit on the underside of horizontal habitats, most likely as shelter from sedimentation (Perog et al., 2023). Oysters are also heavily influenced by the rugosity, or texture, of their substrate. Native Olympia oysters recruited at higher density and percent cover to shelled and rough-textured substrate at higher elevations than typical for the species (Perog et al., 2023). Therefore, dead oyster shells were embedded into the surface of the reef balls to recruit native oysters. Other factors that could influence recruitment success include wind and wave exposure. Generally, with larvae stages of organisms, there tends to be higher recruitment of larvae on the leeward sides of habitat than the windward (Boehlert et al., 1994). As waves crash onto one side of the reef ball, this may cause

stranding of the oyster larvae attempting to attach to the surface. Studies have found that significant wave action can be a primary cause of larvae death (Stoll, S. and Beeck, P. (2011). The disturbance of the high wave can crush and kill the larvae or sweep the larvae away from the targeted settlement substrate completely (Reidenbach et al., 2009).

2.6 Hypotheses and Predictions

Our first research question is: do non-native *M. gigas* oysters occupy more space than native *O. lurida* on reef balls? Our alternative hypothesis is that non-native oysters will occupy more space on the reef balls than native oysters. This predication is due to the larger size of non-native oysters in comparison to native oysters. *O. lurida* size ranges from 12-66 mm (Wasson et al., 2015) and *M. gigas* size ranges from 20-140 mm (Stagličić et al., 2020). The second research question asks: does tidal elevation affect oyster recruitment on reef balls? Our alternative hypothesis is that there will be higher abundance of native oysters (*O. lurida*) at lower elevations and higher abundance of non-native oysters (*M. gigas*) at higher tidal elevations on reef balls. This prediction is based on known zonation patterns of both species. *O. lurida* recruits at a low tidal elevation of +0.2 m MLLW and *M. gigas* recruits at a high tidal elevation of +0.4 m MLLW (Tronske et al., 2018). The final research question asks: do wind and waves affect oyster recruitment on reef balls? Our alternative hypothesis predicts that there will be a higher abundance of *O. lurida* and *M. gigas* on the leeward sides of reef balls than the windward sides due to high wave action from the bay on the windward side. This prediction was constructed based on the idea that increased wave action would more easily knock off small oyster larvae attempting to settle onto the reef balls and that the larvae on the leeward sides of reef balls would be able to recruit more effectively, causing higher densities of oysters on the leeward side. The

effects of tidal elevation as well as wind and wave action on living shorelines consisting of man-made reef balls will affect recruitment of native and non-indigenous oysters on the West Coast of Southern California. There will be a higher percent coverage of native oysters at lower tidal elevations and increased density on leeward orientations of the reef balls.

3. Methodology

3.1 Reef Ball Deployment

Reef balls were deployed into the mudflats of the San Diego Bay at the Chula Vista Wildlife Reserve (CVWR) in January of 2022 and allowed one year for oyster recruitment. There were 360 total reef balls split up into six blocks (A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, and C2) (Fig. 1). Blocks A1, B1, and C1 were placed at a high elevation at 0.5 to 2.5 ft, based on known *O. lurida* and *M. gigas* zonation patterns (Fig. 2, Left) (Tronske et al., 2018). Blocks A2, B2, and C2 were placed at lower elevation at -0.5 to +1.5 ft. Although each block was treated at different elevations, elevation for each reef ball measuring from the top of the ball to the mudflat was recorded. Within each block, five columns of three reef ball arrays were placed. Within an array are four reef balls, each labeled as A, B, C, or D (Fig 2, Right).

Figure 1. Reef ball deployment site layout for reef balls deployed in January 2022 in the Chula Vista Wildlife Reserve, San Diego Bay, CA, USA. Treatments A, B, and C with high and low tidal elevation blocks.

Figure 2. (Left) Close up view of treatment A, blocks A1 and A2 (LOCATION). Five columns of three reef ball arrays and control block (C-A2). (Right) Close up of a reef ball array displaying the offshore and inshore reef balls.

3.2 Reef Ball Surveys

In January of 2023, all 360 reef balls were randomly surveyed for density and size of *O. lurida* and *M. gigas*. A random y-coordinate, direction (in degrees), and surface (inside/outside) was determined for each reef ball. A 15x25 cm quadrat was placed with the random y-coordinate and direction being the center of the quadrat. The y-coordinate was found by placing a meter stick on the top of the reef ball as a reference point and using a second meter stick to find how many centimeters down from the top reference point the quadrat would be placed. Direction was found using cellular device compass applications and was determined to be classified as either leeward or windward. Leeward was between 60 degrees (East) and 180 degrees (South) and windward was between 240 degrees (West) and 360 degrees (North). These orientations were based on the San Diego International Airport Wind Rose (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. San Diego International Airport Wind Rose as input for SWAN modeling. Windward indicated between 240 and 360 degrees, and leeward indicated as between 60 and 180 degrees.

The number of live and dead oysters were counted per quadrat. Quality of oyster counts was ensured by excluding oysters that were halfway or more outside the perimeter of the quadrat. The

size of up to five oysters was recorded in which the length was determined to be from the umbo of the oyster to the furthest extension of the valve. The width was determined as the perpendicular measurement to the length and was the widest point across the oyster valve. A picture of each quadrat was taken to allow for further processing.

3.3 ImageJ Processing

Each image of reef ball survey quadrats was then processed in the program ImageJ to determine the percent cover of oysters. The image was cropped down to the quadrat height and width and a 90–100-point grid was laid over the inside of the perimeter of the quadrat. Points were excluded if a hole in the reef ball was visible within the quadrat. Each point was determined as either species of oyster, substrate (reef ball), or other invertebrate organisms such as mussels, tunicate, or sponge. The number of points per category was then divided by the total number of points within the quadrat to calculate the percent cover of the species or substrate.

3.4 Data Analysis

The computer program JMP was used to analyze the data. A 4-way ANOVA was conducted testing the effects of species of oyster (*O. lurida* and *M. gigas*), direction, surface (inside/outside), and tidal elevation by block treatment (High = 0.5-2.5 ft, Low = -0.5-+1.5 ft) against percent cover of oysters. To analyze oyster densities per quadrat, the total number of oysters was divided by the area per quadrat (m²) which was calculated by multiplying the length by the width (cm) and converting to meters. A 3-way ANOVA was conducted testing the effects of quadrat tidal elevation (m MLLW), direction (leeward/windward), and surface (inside/outside) on *O. lurida* density. For *M. gigas* density, only 7% of the quadrats (25/360) had any *M. gigas*

present: 93% of quadrats lacked *M. gigas* entirely precluding our ability to perform statistical analyses (because the data were extremely non-normal and heteroscedastic) therefore the data was graphed and visually inspected for patterns.

4. Observations and Results

4.1 Field Observations

Per observations in the field, large clusters of oysters were seen near the bottom of most reef balls around the entire circumference of the ball. There were higher densities of oysters on the outside surface of the ball rather than the inside. *O. lurida* densities were higher than *M. gigas* densities, however, size of *M. gigas* was greater than size of *O. lurida*. Oysters did not usually recruit on the horizontal base of the reef ball; only vertical settlement was observed. Some oysters were also seen to be settled within the holes of the reef balls.

4.2 Oyster Percent Cover

Figure 4 shows the percent cover of the two species, *M. gigas* and *O. lurida*, in which percent cover and species is separated by direction (leeward or windward) and inside or outside of the reef ball. For each species, the data was also separated by high (blue) and low (red) elevation blocks. In no case did *M. gigas* occupy more space on the reef balls and *O. lurida* only significantly occupied more space than *M. gigas* on the outside of reef balls at low tidal elevation blocks. No effect of direction on percent cover for either species was detected. A 3-way affect was found to be significant ($p=0.03$) with species, direction, and tidal elevation. An additional 3-

way affect was also found to be significant ($p=0.04$) for species, inside/outside, and tidal elevation (Fig. 3).

Figure 4. *M. gigas* and *O. lurida* percent cover inside and outside of reef balls on the leeward and windward sides in CVWR, San Diego, CA, USA 1 year after deployment. *O. lurida* cover was greater than *M. gigas* but only consistently on the outside of reef balls on the low-elevation blocks (4-way ANOVA, species*direction*elevation, $p=0.03$, species*in/out* elevation, $p=0.04$).

4.3 Oyster Density

A significant effect ($p<0.0001$) of tidal elevation and inside/outside was found. The density of *O. lurida* was found to decline as tidal elevation decreased, however, was only found significant on the outside of reef balls and not the inside. There was no effect of tidal elevation on the inside of

reef balls for *O. lurida* (Fig. 5). *M. gigas* density increased with quadrat tidal elevation, however, only on the inside of reef balls. No effect of leeward or windward was found for either species.

Figure 5. *M. gigas* (top panel) and *O. lurida* density as a function of tidal elevation (m MLLW) and wave exposure on the inside and outside of reef balls in CVWR, San Diego, CA, USA 1 year after deployment. *O. lurida* density declined with elevation but more significantly on the outside of reef balls (3-way ANOVA, elevation*in/out, $p < 0.0001$).

Response Variable	Source	df	Sum Squares	F ratio	P
Percent cover	Elev	1	26.156678	25.7679	<.0001
	Species	1	97.506638	96.0572	<.0001
	Elev*Species	1	32.363042	31.882	<.0001
	Direction	1	0.707295	0.6968	0.4043
	Elev*Direction	1	2.660448	2.6209	0.1061
	Species*Direction	1	0.356819	0.3515	0.5535
	Elev*Species*Direction	1	4.600991	4.5326	0.0338
	Inside/Outside	1	25.905515	25.5204	<.0001
	Elev*Inside/Outside	1	6.099011	6.0084	0.0146
	Species*Inside/Outside	1	27.566182	27.1564	<.0001
	Elev*Species*Inside/Outside	1	4.37003	4.3051	0.0385
	Direction*Inside/Outside	1	0.129519	0.1276	0.7211
	Elev*Direction*Inside/Outside	1	0.03019	0.0297	0.8632
	Species*Direction*Inside/Outside	1	0.015924	0.0157	0.9004
	Elev*Species*Direction*Inside/Outside	1	0.424744	0.4184	0.518
	Error		478	485.21258	
C. Total		493	749.72201		
<hr/>					
<i>O. lurida</i>					
Density	Direction	1	5.3096	0.1161	0.7337
				137.204	
	Tidal Elevation of Quadrat (m)(MLLW)	1	6274.3254	9	<.0001
	Direction*Tidal Elevation of Quadrat (m)(MLLW)	1	72.4054	1.5833	0.2099
	Error		186	8505.706	
C. Total		189	15190.061		

Table 1

Four-way ANOVA effect test statistics for effects of tidal elevation (=elev), species (*O. lurida* and *M. gigas*), direction, and inside/outside of reef balls deployed in January of 2022 in the San Diego Bay, CA, USA. Bold indicates significant p-value.

5. Discussion

5.1 Percent Cover and Oyster Density

The first research question that was asked was: “Do non-native oysters occupy more space than native oyster species on reef balls?” in which we can confidently say no, non-native oysters do not occupy more space on reef balls than native oysters. This was seen in Figure 3 in which *M. gigas* did not reach a higher percent cover than *O. lurida* in any case on the reef balls. This was due to the high density of native oysters found to recruit onto the reef balls. Therefore, we can accept the null hypothesis that non-native oysters will not occupy more space on the reef balls than native oysters and reject the alternative hypothesis. This finding contradicts previous studies that have found *M. gigas* to occupy more space than *O. lurida* oysters (Perog et al., 2023). However, this may be because reef balls were surveyed only one year after deployment. An accumulation of oysters in additional years may come to find a higher percent cover of non-native oysters because of their large size.

The second and third research questions ask if tidal elevation and wind/wave action influence oyster recruitment onto reef balls. Figure 4 shows oyster density for both native and non-native oysters and the effects of tidal elevation as well as direction of wind/wave impact. We found that tidal elevation significantly affects the recruitment of both *M. gigas* and *O. lurida*, however, on different locations on the reef balls. *O. lurida* density was only found to be significantly higher than *M. gigas* on the outside of reef balls in which density decreased as quadrat tidal elevation increased. The opposite was true for *M. gigas* in which density increased with increasing quadrat tidal elevation. The high density of native oysters on the outside of reef balls is most likely due

to the high rugosity of the reef ball substrate. The outside was much higher in rugosity than the inside which may have encourage oyster recruitment significantly. We can accept the second alternative hypothesis that there will be higher abundance of native oysters at lower tidal elevations and higher abundance of non-native oysters at higher tidal elevations on reef balls and reject the null hypothesis. We can also accept the null hypothesis that there will not be a higher abundance of *O. lurida* and *M. gigas* on the leeward sides of reef balls than the windward sides due to high wave action from the bay on the windward side and reject the null hypothesis. These patterns make sense due to already known habitat zonation patterns of both native and non-native oysters. *O. lurida* typically recruits within a low tidal elevation of +0.2 m MLLW and *M. gigas* recruits at a higher tidal elevation of +0.4 m MLLW. Since these zonation patterns overlap, we expected overlap of recruitment onto reef balls which is true for our results.

5.2 Sources of Error

During the surveys at the field site there possibly could have been data collection errors which may inaccurately represent the patterns of oyster recruitment on the reef balls. Cellular devices were used for determining the degrees of orientation per quadrat. Upon further examination of the performance of the compass application, we discovered that there is approximately a 30-degree difference for the same coordinate among the various cellular devices used by lab team members. The method in which orientation was determined may have also varied amongst lab team members and the method may have not been consistent throughout surveying the reef balls. Due to these possible errors, it is suggested that the same experiment should be repeated whilst improving the synchrony of orientation determination methodology amongst the lab team as well as a more accurate instrument for determining orientation degrees.

6. Conclusions

6.1 Study Summary

The eroding shorelines of the west coast of the United States and the severely declining populations of native oysters has inspired the living shoreline project funded by the Port of the San Diego. The goals of the living shoreline project are to restore native oysters while simultaneously protecting and preventing further erosion along the shorelines. Reef balls were engineered to provide complex habitat for oysters to recruit onto and help other organisms within the bay. Both native and non-native oyster recruitment was analyzed one year after reef balls were placed in the San Diego Bay. *O. lurida* had significantly occupied more space than *M. gigas* on the outside of reef balls at low tidal elevations and was also found to decrease in density as tidal elevation increased. *M. gigas* densities increased with tidal elevation but only significantly on the inside of reef balls. The most compelling finding, however, was no effect of wind or wave action on oyster recruitment for either species. These results will provide the Port of San Diego with important data on how to further adjust the building and construction of living shorelines to restore the population of native oysters most efficiently.

6.2 Future studies

To reassess the effect of wind and wave action on oyster recruitment onto reef balls, the density of native and non-native oysters must be analyzed differently. Due to the possible bias of reef balls shielding other reef balls within an array of four reef balls, the analysis must group together reef balls A, B, and D together and compare the densities on the windward and leeward sides of

the reef balls with reef ball position C. This is to eliminate the factor of reef balls A, B, and D shielding reef ball C from wind and wave action. Other future studies may look at the effect of living shorelines on oyster populations in different environments, such as along northern coasts with differing wind and wave action against the reef balls.

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References

- Alan C. Trimble, Jennifer L. Ruesink, and Brett R. Dumbauld. (2009). "Factors Preventing the Recovery of a Historically Overexploited Shellfish Species, *Ostrea lurida* Carpenter 1864," *Journal of Shellfish Research* 28(1), 97-106, <https://doi.org/10.2983/035.028.0116>.
- Baggett, Lesley & Powers, Sean & Brumbaugh, Robert & Coen, Loren & DeAngelis, Bryan & Greene, Jennifer & Hancock, Boze & Morlock, Summer. (2014). *Oyster Habitat Restoration Monitoring and Assessment Handbook*.
- Beck, M.W., Brumbaugh, R.D., Airoidi, L., Carranza, A., Coen, L.D., Crawford, C., Defeo, O., Edgar, G.J., Hancock, B., Kay, M.C., Lenihan, H.S., Luckenbach, M.W., Toropova, C.L., Zhang, G., Guo, X., (2011). Oyster reefs at risk and recommendations for conservation, restoration, and management. *BioScience* 61 (2), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2011.61.2.5>.
- Boehlert, G. W., & Mundy, B. C. (1994). Vertical and onshore-offshore distributional patterns of tuna larvae in relation to physical habitat features. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 107(1/2), 1–13. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24844774>.
- Buccino, M., Del Vita, I., Calabrese, M., 2014. Engineering modeling of wave transmission of reef balls. *J. Waterway Port Coast. Ocean Eng.* 140 (4) [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)WW.1943-5460.0000237](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)WW.1943-5460.0000237).
- Dias, J. M., Gómez-Gesteira, J., De Castro, M., Iglesias, D., Sousa, M., ElSerafy, G., & Dias, J. M. (2022). Historical and future naturalization of *Magallana gigas* in the Galician coast

- in a context of climate change. *Science of the Total Environment*, 838, 156437.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.156437>
- Dyer, K. (1973). *Estuaries: a physical introduction*. <https://www.vliz.be/en/imis?refid=83760>.
- Griggs, G.B., 2009. The effects of armoring shorelines - the California experience. In: Puget Sound Shorelines and the Impacts of Armoring—Proceedings of a State of the Science Workshop, p. 8. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/268335363_The_Effects_of_Armoring_Shorelines-The_California_Experience (accessed 14 May 2023).
- Hamester, M. R. R., Balzer, P. S., & Becker, D. (2012). Characterization of calcium carbonate obtained from oyster and mussel shells and incorporation in polypropylene. *Materials Research-ibero-american Journal of Materials*, 15(2), 204–208.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/s1516-14392012005000014>.
- Hartig, E. K., Gornitz, V., Kolker, A., Mushacke, F., & Fallon, D. (2002). Anthropogenic and Climate-Change Impacts on Salt Marshes of Jamaica Bay, New York City. *Wetlands*, 22, 71-89. [https://doi.org/10.1672/0277-5212\(2002\)022\[0071:AACCIO\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1672/0277-5212(2002)022[0071:AACCIO]2.0.CO;2).
- Latta, M., Boyer, K., 2015. San Francisco Bay Living Shorelines: Nearshore Linkages Project Summary of Key Findings Two Years Post-Installation. San Francisco Bay Living Shorelines Project. http://www.sfbaylivingshorelines.org/sf_shorelines_documents.html [accessed 22 May, 2023].
- Parker, V.T., Boyer, K.E., (2019). Sea-level rise and climate change impacts on an urbanized pacific coast estuary. *Wetlands* 39 (6), 1219–1232. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-017-0980-7>.
- Perog, B. D., Bowers-Doerning, C., Ramirez, C. Y. L., Marks, A. N., Torres, R. F., Jr, Wolfe, M. L., & Zacherl, D. C. (2023). Shell cover, rugosity, and tidal elevation impact native and non-indigenous oyster recruitment: Implications for reef ball design. *Ecological Engineering*, 192, 106969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2023.106969>.
- Ridlon, A. D., Marks, A., Zabin, C. J., Zacherl, D., Allen, B., Crooks, J., Fleener, G., Grosholz, E., Peabody, B., Toft, J., & Wasson, K. (2021). Conservation of Marine Foundation Species: Learning from Native Oyster Restoration from California to British Columbia. *Estuaries and Coasts*, 44, 1723-1743. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-021-00920-7>.
- Reidenbach, Matthew A., Koseff, Jeffrey R., Koehl, M. A. R., (2009), Hydrodynamic forces on larvae affect their settlement on coral reefs in turbulent, wave-driven flow, *Limnology and Oceanography*, 54, doi: 10.4319/lo.2009.54.1.0318.
- Schaefer, M.B., 1937. Attachment of the larvae of *Ostrea gigas*, the Japanese oyster, to plane surfaces. *Ecology* 18 (4), 523–527. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1930578>.
- Stagličić, N., Šegvić-Bubić, T., Ezgeta-Balić, D., Varezić, D. B., Grubišić, L., Žuvić, L., Lin, Y., & Briski, E. (2020). Distribution patterns of two co-existing oyster species in the northern Adriatic Sea: The native European flat oyster *Ostrea edulis* and the non-native Pacific oyster *Magallana gigas*. *Ecological Indicators*, 113, 106233.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106233>.

- Stoll, S. and Beeck, P. (2011), Post-release stranding rates of stocked allis shad (*Alosa alosa*) larvae exposed to surface wave action. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 27: 41-44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0426.2011.01879.x>
- Trimble AC, Ruesink JL, Dumbauld BR (2009) Factors preventing the recovery of a historically overexploited shellfish species, *Ostrea lurida carpenter* 1864. *Journal of Shellfish Research* 28:97–106. <https://doi.org/10.2983/035.028.0116>.
- Tronske, N. B., Parker, T. A., Henderson, H. D., Burnaford, J. L., & Zacherl, D. (2018). Densities and Zonation Patterns of Native and Non-Indigenous Oysters in Southern California Bays. *Wetlands*, 38, 1313-1326. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-018-1055-0>
- Wasson, K., et al. (2015). A Guide to Olympia Oyster Restoration and Conservation. <https://www.sfbaysubtidal.org/OYSTERGUIDE-FULL-LORES.pdf>.
- Zu Ermgassen, P. S., Spalding, M. D., Blake, B., Coen, L. D., Dumbauld, B., Geiger, S., Grabowski, J. H., Grizzle, R., Luckenbach, M., McGraw, K., Rodney, W., Ruesink, J. L., Powers, S. P., & Brumbaugh, R. (2012). Historical ecology with real numbers: past and present extent and biomass of an imperilled estuarine habitat. *Proceedings of The Royal Society Biological Sciences*, 279, 3393-3400. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2012.0313>